

Example Data Management Plan – concise version

Transcriptome analysis of diabetes type 1 patients and mouse models

Data Stewardship Wizard (DSW) Example Data Management Plan

Concise version

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Based on

Based on Standard DMP template for Biotechnology and Biological Sciences Research Council (BB-SRC) 2024

Funded by the [ELIXIR-UK: FAIR Data Stewardship training UKRI award](#) (MR/V038966/1) and BioFAIR

I. Data areas and data types

This study will generate quantitative measurements of gene/transcript expression from human blood using bulk RNAseq, and reuse mouse gene/transcript expression data from publicly available microarray and bulk RNAseq studies.

- **Human bulk RNAseq:**
 - **Platform:** Illumina HiSeq 2500 (100bp paired-end, sequencing depth of ~45M read pairs).
 - **Data format:** compressed FASTQ.
 - **Scale:** 12 control samples (patients) and 12 disease samples (diabetes type 1 patients).
 - **TOTAL file size:** estimated 150 GB.
- **Mouse transcriptomics:** (these are public datasets from ArrayExpress and GEO, and will not be archived by this study):
 - **Platforms:** mixed (both expression microarray and RNAseq).
 - **Data formats:** compressed FASTQ, CEL, text.
 - **Scale:** estimated 50 samples.
 - **TOTAL file size:** estimated 100-400GB.

II. Standards and metadata

RNAseq data and associated metadata will be annotated to the level required by the public repository, ArrayExpress ([ebi.ac.uk/arrayexpress](https://www.ebi.ac.uk/arrayexpress)), employing the community metadata standard: MINSEQE (doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5706412). Metadata standards enable FAIR: discovery, download, interoperability and reuse.

III. Relationship to other data available in public repositories

New primary data (FASTQ) will be generated for human blood not currently available in public repositories. This study will also use mouse gene/transcript expression data from publicly available microarray and bulk RNAseq studies.

IV. Secondary use

This data will be of benefit for the type 1 diabetes research community and complements mouse model data in the public domain (URL).

V. Methods for data sharing

All new data generated will be bulk RNAseq. All raw data (FASTQ)

and processed data (gene/transcript unnormalised counts) will be available to all via the public repository, ArrayExpress (ebi.ac.uk/arrayexpress). ArrayExpress indexes metadata to enable discovery and download.

VI. Proprietary data

We envisage no restrictions or delays to data sharing.

VII. Timeframes

Data will be shared publicly via ArrayExpress at the time of publication or within 3 years of its generation.

VIII. Format of the final dataset

Final dataset will be FASTQ (raw) and gene/transcript read counts per sample (processed, csv).